

Supplementary Material

Text

Element mapping of recovered samples was conducted for 3 h by a Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM) (Magellan 400) equipped with an Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (EDS) at the State Key Laboratory of Superhard Materials, Jilin University.

Figures

Fig.S1. Two-dimensional X-ray diffraction patterns of each recovered sample collected for three hours (one hour/frame in the range 25-85° for 2 theta). The diffraction patterns in Fig. S1a-e present only few spots due to the fact that only few crystals are inside the 100 micron diffraction beam as expected due to the large grain size of the bridgmanite crystals. In Fig.S1f, instead, diffracted lines are visible indicating that the bridgmanite crystals have a smaller grain size.

Fig.S2. Optical micrographs of recovered samples in transmitted light. We can observe inclusions inside grains or along grain boundaries.

Fig.S3. Representative BSE images of run products under high magnification in runs S7119, IRIS680, IRIS669, and S7158. Abbreviations: Gar, garnet; Brg, bridgmanite; Sti, stishovite; Ph D: phase D; Per, periclase; Hym, hydrous melt.

Fig.S4. Element mapping of the recovered sample in run IRIS669.

Fig.S5. Element mapping of the recovered sample in run IRIS680.

Fig. S7. FTIR spectra on spots of single crystals of aluminous bridgmanite (S-Brg) coexisting with hydrous melts (Hym) in run S7139, where a-d are the measured spots. The inset picture is an optical micrograph of the sample in transmitted light.

Fig. S8. Optical micrograph and typical FTIR spectra of single-crystal (S) or polycrystalline (P) aluminous bridgmanite (Brg) coexisting with phase D, brucite (Bru), and trace amounts of hydrous melt (Hym) in run IRIS680, where a-c represent the measured spots. Stars (*) represent vibrations of C-H from the FTIR system.

Fig. S9. FTIR spectra on single-crystal (S) and aggregates of polycrystalline (P) (Fe, Al)-bearing bridgmanite coexisting with brucite (Bru) and hydrous melt (Hym) in run S7158, where a-c represent the measured spots. The inset picture is an optical micrograph of the sample in transmitted light.

Table S1 Chemical composition of the synthesized (Fe, Al)-bearing bridgmanite in runs S7158 and H4851

Run. No.	S7158			H4851		
	Brg (n = 22)	Fp (n=4)	Hym (n=4)	Brg (n = 22)	Fp (n=2)	Hym (n=2)
MgO	37.13(34)	95.01 (21)	44.90 (85)	36.46(71)	98.49 (19)	43.39 (43)
Al ₂ O ₃	4.28 (16)	0.25 (0)	3.07 (14)	4.55 (101)	0.30 (2)	2.43 (9)
FeO	4.21 (35)	4.58 (10)	12.90 (61)	5.79 (92)	0.36 (6)	1.63 (3)
SiO ₂	54.27 (37)	0.02 (2)	3.89 (24)	52.96 (157)	0.01 (1)	6.59 (37)
Total	99.89(51)	99.86 (16)	64.75 (50)	99.76(62)	99.15 (13)	45.73 (136)
Fe ³⁺ /ΣFe	84 (8)					
Mg	0.933 (6)	0.972 (1)	1.114 (21)	0.926 (13)	0.972 (1)	1.077 (11)
Al	0.086 (4)	0.002 (0)	0.060 (3)	0.092 (21)	0.002 (0)	0.048 (2)
Fe ³⁺	0.050 (5)		0.177 (8)	0.0810(13)		0.022 (0)
Fe ²⁺	0.010 (1)	0.026 (1)			0.002 (0)	
Si	0.922 (5)	0	0.065 (4)	0.902 (23)	0	0.110 (6)
O	2.989 (3)	1	1.599 (15)	2.988 (9)	1	1.256 (19)
Component (mol%)						
MgSiO ₃	91 (1)			90 (2)		
FeSiO ₃	1 (0)					
FeAlO ₃ (FCC)	5 (1)			8 (2)		
AlAlO ₃ (CC)	1 (0)					
MgAlO _{2.5} (OV)	2 (1)			1 (1)		
Mg(Fe _{0.5} Al _{0.5})O _{2.5} (OV)				1 (1)		
Total	100			100		

Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; Fp, ferropriclas; Hym, hydrous melt.

n: number of analysis points

number in parentheses represents the error for the last digit.